

The International Conference on Solid Compounds of Transition Elements

SCTE 2021

April 12 – 15, 2021
Wrocław, Poland

organized by

Institute of Low Temperature
and Structure Research,
Polish Academy of Sciences,
Wrocław, Poland

Programme and abstracts

Wednesday 7A

Recovery of mining waste as source of raw material for the synthesis of tetrahedrite-tennantite materials

F. Neves¹, L. Esperto¹, I. Figueira¹, J. Mascarenhas¹, R. Salgueiro², T.P. Silva², J.B. Correia¹, P.A. Carvalho^{3,4}, D. de Oliveira²

¹*LNEG, Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, Estrada do Paço do Lumiar, 22, 1649-038 Lisboa, Portugal*

²*LNEG, Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, Estrada da Portela, Bairro do Zambujal – Alfragide, Apartado 7586, 2610-999 Amadora, Portugal*

³*SINTEF Materials Physics, Forskningsveien 1 NO-0373 Oslo, Norway*

⁴*CeFEMA, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Av. Rovisco Pais 1, 1000-049 Lisboa, Portugal*

e-mail: filipe.neves@lneg.pt

The present study intends to demonstrate the feasibility of the direct incorporation of tetrahedrite-tennantite (td-tn) dump material as raw material in the processing cycle of td-tn materials ($\text{Cu}_{12-x}(\text{TM})_x(\text{Sb,As})_4\text{S}_{13}$, TM – transition metal) through mechanochemical synthesis (MCS). This was evaluated by preparing powder mixtures containing different mass ratios (20% to 80%) of td-tn dump material (collected in the waste dumps of the abandoned Barrigão copper mine, located in the Portuguese zone of the Iberian Pyrite Belt) and synthetic tetrahedrite (syn-td, prepared by MCS). MCS was done on a planetary ball mill at 340 rpm/ 2 h. Uniaxially pressed pellets from the MCS powders were heat-treated (HT) in vacuum between 350°C – 450 °C. Phase formation/chemical homogeneity was investigated using X-ray diffraction, transmission and scanning electron microscopy.

The MCS have led to an increase in the amount of the td-tn phase and to a complete dissolution of the dump material sulfides with the syn-td constituents resulting in the formation of a td-tn solid solution with Fe. Quartz was present in all MCS powders, while Cu_3SbS_4 was observed in the mixtures with 20% dump material. No phase decomposition was observed with HT. The obtained results are of major relevance in light of their potential environmental benefits and show that the approach followed represents an opportunity to recover valuable resources.

Ack: This work is funded by national funds through the FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P., under the project PTDC/EAM-PEC/29905/2017 (<http://localenergy.lneg.pt>). The “Direção Geral de Energia e Geologia” participates as an External Advisor in LocalEnergy project.

Recovery of mining waste as source of raw material for the synthesis of tetrahedrite-tennantite materials

Filipe Neves¹, L. Esperto¹, I. Figueira¹, J. Mascarenhas¹, R. Salgueiro², T.P. Silva², J.B. Correia¹, P.A. Carvalho^{3,4}, D. de Oliveira²

¹ LNEG, Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, Estrada do Paço do Lumiar, 22, 1649-038 Lisboa, Portugal

²LNEG, Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, Estrada da Portela, Bairro do Zambujal – Alfragide, Apartado 7586, 2610-999 Amadora, Portugal

³SINTEF Materials Physics, Forskningsveien 1 NO-0373 Oslo, Norway

⁴CeFEMA, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Av. Rovisco Pais 1, 1000-049 Lisboa, Portugal

e-mail: filipe.neves@lneg.pt

OUTLINE

- MOTIVATION
- OBJECTIVE
- EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS
- RESULTS
- CONCLUSIONS
- ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

MOTIVATION

Multidisciplinary Research, Development and Innovation project, involving activities in the field of materials science, geology and renewable energies

One of the research topics is the development of tetrahedrite-based thermoelectric materials

Natural and synthetic tetrahedrites

<http://localenergy.lneg.pt/>

MOTIVATION

Synthetic tetrahedrite-based materials have already demonstrated exceptional properties and are promising materials for thermoelectric applications

Tetrahedrite-tennantite (td-tn) mineral series ($\text{Cu}_{12-x}(\text{TM})_x(\text{Sb,As})_4\text{S}_{13}$, TM – transition metal) is very abundant and can be found in mine waste

This can be a very pertinent observation (Liu et al., 2017) we compare to the rare elements, where some of them are found in only one country

Why is relevant studying tetrahedrite-based materials?
In our opinion, and taking all this into consideration, it is an emerging and key issue to evaluate the use of dump material, as a source of raw material for the synthesis of td-tn materials.

And why is also very important to find sustainable and innovative solutions for the recycling, reuse and rehabilitation of the mine wastes?

Td-tn are considered as “dirty concentrates”:

- serious environmental and economic implications
- implies performing research and innovation studies on waste processing technologies

The td-tn mineral series is commonly associated with the main copper sulfide minerals in ore bodies used in the copper production process

OBJECTIVE

Produce tetrahedrite-tennantite (tn-td) materials

MechanoChemical Synthesis (MCS) (high energy ball milling)

powder mixtures of td-tn dump material / synthetic tetrahedrite (syn-td).

Thermal heat treatments - evaluate the thermal stability of the td-tn phase produced by MCS.

MechanoChemical Synthesis (MCS)

td-tn dump material and syn-td powder mixtures;

Three series of mixtures were produced with 20%, 50% and 80% by weight of the td-tn dump material

High-energy planetary ball mill PM 400/Retsch;

Milling speed: 340 rpm
Total time: 2 h

X40Cr13 stainless steel jars (250 mL) and balls (15 mm), without any additional fluid medium

The jars were sealed, evacuated, and back filled with Ar gas

Ball-to-powder ratio of 20:1

Milling periods of 10 min were alternated with 5 min periods of rest

Thermal heat treatment (HT)

The MCS powders were cold pressed at 260 Mpa

Vacuum (10^{-2} mbar) HT at 350 °C // 400 °C // 450 °C, holding time of 1 h

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The **td-tn dump material** was obtained from collecting ore-bearing hand specimen size samples at the Barrigão mine dumps

Waste dumps of the abandoned **Barrigão copper mine**

Typical td-tn ore samples

Location of the Barrigão deposit in the Portuguese area of the **Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB)**

The IPB is one of the most important volcanogenic massive sulfide districts in the world

The **syn-td powders** were obtained by **MCS**

Target composition

The MCS was conducted using identical experimental conditions described in the previous slide for the (td-tn dump material / syn-td) powder mixtures

Characterization techniques

RESULTS

syn-td powders

multiphase compounds consisting of tetrahedrite, famatinite and skinnerite

RESULTS

td-tn dump material

td-tn-(Fe), richer in As than in Sb,
coexisting with **chalcopyrite** and **quartz**

F. Neves, L. Esperto, I. Figueira, J. Mascarenhas, et al.
Minerals Engineering, 164 (2021) 106833
 doi: 10.1016/j.mineng.2021.106833

	Cu	Fe	Sb	As	S	Sn	Possible mineral formula
Barrigão							
As-tt	31.3±0.5	5.5±0.4	5.5±0.7	11.6±0.8	46.1±0.5		$\text{Cu}_{9.1}\text{Fe}_{1.6}\text{Sb}_{1.6}\text{As}_{3.3}\text{S}_{13.4}$
Sb-tt	31.7±0.2	4.0±0.3	9.7±0.4	7.4±0.1	47.2±0.4		$\text{Cu}_{9.2}\text{Fe}_{1.2}\text{Sb}_{2.8}\text{As}_{2.1}\text{S}_{13.7}$

td-tn dump material /syn-td powder mixtures after 2 h MCS

Morphology and particle size distribution

- **Morphology is quite irregular**, generically presenting two types of fraction: one at the submicrometric scale and the other of the order of a few tens of micrometers.
- The submicron fraction tend to aggregate in micron-sized agglomerates.
- Corroborated by the values of the characteristic dimensions of the particles and by the granulometric distribution.
- D10: 0.81-1.02 µm; **D50: 4.55-5.95 µm**; D90: 23.23-35.25 µm
- The frequency distribution curve (q3, histogram) reveals a **multimodal distribution**.

td-tn dump material /syn-td powder mixtures after 2 h MCS

Typical HAADF-STEM images, and the corresponding EDS elemental maps for the mixture with 50% td-tn dump material

- The chemical mappings revealed that the **main elements** are **evenly distributed** throughout the analyzed particles except for Fe that shows some heterogeneity with stronger signal in some areas.
- Considering the initial constitution of the starting materials, **the uniform distribution of Cu, Sb and As is extremely relevant.**
- The spatial distribution of Si-O-rich areas is associated to the presence of quartz.

RESULTS

td-tn dump material /syn-td powder mixtures after 2 h MCS

Typical XRD patterns

- The complex displacement reactions that occurred during the MCS are here highlighted.
- There was a successful and **fast conversion of the secondary pristine sulfide phases** into the tn-td-(Fe) phase. The exception was for the 20% mixture where famatinite was still indexed.
- The **broadening and shape of the Bragg peaks** can be ascribed to some degree of **amorphization**.
- The **shifting of the Bragg peaks to higher angles** with the **increasing content of td-tn dump material** is associated to a **linear reduction in the lattice parameter**, following the Vegard's law, consistent with the formation of a (Cu,Fe)₁₂(Sb,As)₄S₁₃ solid solution.

RESULTS

td-tn dump material /syn-td powder mixtures after MCS + HT

Typical XRD patterns, here exemplified for the mixture with 50% td-tn dump material

- The overall results did not show significant changes in the identified phases with the HTs.
- However, the Bragg peaks became sharper with the increase of the temperature because of the increase of the crystallite size and reduction of internal strains.

RESULTS

td-tn dump material /syn-td powder mixtures after MCS + HT

DIFFRAC.TOPAS Rietveld quantitative analysis (wt%)									
	td-tn	famatinite	skinnerite	quartz	chalcopyrite	cubanite	amorphous	Rwp	
syn-td (2 h MCS)	34	18	13				36	3.48	
td-tn dump material	63			6	31			10.6	
									wt% of td-tn already present before MCS
20% - 2 h MCS	72	3		2			23	4.8	40
350 °C/ 1 h	95	3		2				7.7	
400 °C/ 1 h	88	5		7				9.1	
450 °C/ 1h	98	1		1				9.4	
50% - 2 h MCS	69			3			28	6.0	49
350 °C/ 1h	98			2				7.8	
400 °C/ 1h	97			3				8.4	
450 °C/ 1h	98			2				8.5	
80% - 2 h MCS	62			4			34	7	57
350 °C/ 1 h	93	3		4				8.6	
400 °C/ 1 h	92			2		6		8.1	
450 °C/1 h	97			3				8.9	

RESULTS

td-tn dump material /syn-td powder mixtures after MCS + HT

Typical SEM/BSE images, here exemplified for the mixtures HT at 400 °C/ 1h

$(\text{Cu,Fe})_{12}(\text{Sb,As})_4\text{S}_{13}$	Possible formula based on EDS (average of 6 point analysis)		
	20%	50%	80%
350 °C/ 1 h	$\text{Cu}_{10.8}\text{Fe}_{0.6}\text{Sb}_{4.0}\text{As}_{0.9}\text{S}_{12.7}$	$\text{Cu}_{10.0}\text{Fe}_{1.2}\text{Sb}_{3.0}\text{As}_{2.2}\text{S}_{12.6}$	$\text{Cu}_{10.0}\text{Fe}_{1.8}\text{Sb}_{2.0}\text{As}_{3.1}\text{S}_{12.1}$
400 °C/ 1 h	$\text{Cu}_{12.0}\text{Fe}_{0.6}\text{Sb}_{3.8}\text{As}_{0.8}\text{S}_{11.8}$	$\text{Cu}_{10.4}\text{Fe}_{1.3}\text{Sb}_{3.1}\text{As}_{2.1}\text{S}_{12.1}$	$\text{Cu}_{9.9}\text{Fe}_{1.8}\text{Sb}_{2.0}\text{As}_{3.1}\text{S}_{12.2}$
450 °C/ 1 h	$\text{Cu}_{11.2}\text{Fe}_{0.7}\text{Sb}_{4.1}\text{As}_{0.8}\text{S}_{12.2}$	$\text{Cu}_{9.8}\text{Fe}_{1.5}\text{Sb}_{3.2}\text{As}_{2.0}\text{S}_{12.5}$	$\text{Cu}_{9.8}\text{Fe}_{2.2}\text{Sb}_{2.4}\text{As}_{2.8}\text{S}_{11.8}$
2 h MCS	$\text{Cu}_{10.6}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Sb}_{3.8}\text{As}_{0.8}\text{S}_{13.2}$	$\text{Cu}_{9.7}\text{Fe}_{1.3}\text{Sb}_{2.9}\text{As}_{1.9}\text{S}_{13.1}$	$\text{Cu}_{9.9}\text{Fe}_{1.4}\text{Sb}_{1.9}\text{As}_{2.9}\text{S}_{13.0}$

CONCLUSIONS

- The obtained results demonstrate the viability of using tetrahedrite-tennantite dump material, collected in the Barrigão mine dumps, for the synthesis of tetrahedrite-based materials.
- Full conversion of the secondary pristine sulfide phases into the tn-td-(Fe) phase with the mechanochemical synthesis process (small % of farnatinitite still identified in the mixtures with 20% td-tn dump material). Quartz present in all mixtures.
- No significant phase changes were observed with the heat treatments beyond 350 °C.
- The possibility of adding even a small percentage of dump material in the processing cycle of tetrahedrite-based materials is relevant and can be considered as a sustainable and innovative approach for the recycling of the waste mines.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

<http://localenergy.lneg.pt>

This work is funded by national funds through the FCT - Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P., under the project PTDC/EAM-PEC/29905/2017

FCT Fundação
para a Ciência
e a Tecnologia

 **REPÚBLICA
PORTUGUESA**

The “Direção Geral de Energia e Geologia” participates as an
“External Advisor” in LocalEnergy project.

Thank You For Your Attention

filipe.neves@lneg.pt

Related studies

F. Neves, L. Esperto, I. Figueira, J. Mascarenhas, R. Salgueiro, T.P. Silva, J.B. Correia, P. A. Carvalho, D. de Oliveira

Mechanochemical synthesis of tetrahedrite materials using mixtures of synthetic and ore samples collected in the Portuguese zone of the Iberian Pyrite Belt

Minerals Engineering, 164 (2021) 106833

doi: [**10.1016/j.mineng.2021.106833**](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2021.106833)

D. de Oliveira, R. Salgueiro, T.P. Silva, F. Reiser, F. Guimarães, F. Neves

The Barrigão copper deposit: tennantite-tetrahedrite for thermoelectric and high-technology applications

Extended Abstracts of CIG 2019, XII Congresso Ibérico de Geoquímica/XX Semana da Geoquímica, 22-26 Setembro de 2019, Évora, Portugal, Pages 255-258, (2019)

doi: [**10.5281/zenodo.4618201**](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4618201)

Beatriz Santos, Elsa Lopes, Filipe Neves, António Pereira Gonçalves

Natural Alternatives for Thermoelectric Materials

Oral presentation at SCTE 2021 (April 12th, 2021, session 1A), page 25 of the SCTE 2021 abstract booklet.

António Pereira Gonçalves

Thermoelectric tetrahedrites: from materials to devices

Oral presentation at SCTE 2021 (April 12th, 2021, session 1A), page 23 of the SCTE 2021 abstract booklet.